

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Acronyms and abbreviations

CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
BoM	Bill of Materials
GWP	Global Warming Potential
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MS	Milestone
PC	Project Coordinator
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Glossary of key terms¹:

Bill of materials
A bill of materials (BoM) is a list of the parts or components that are required to build a product. For each of the components the precise type and amount of material is listed.
Biological cycles
In biological cycles, non-toxic materials are restored into the biosphere while rebuilding natural capital, after being cascaded into different applications.
Circular economy
A circular economy is a global economic model that decouples economic growth and development from the consumption of finite resources. It is restorative by design, and aims to keep products, components and materials at their highest utility and value, at all times.
Closed loop
In a closed loop, used products come back to the original manufacturer and components or materials are used again to produce new products of the same type.
Feedstock
Feedstock is anything used to produce a new product. This in particular includes raw materials (from either virgin or recycled sources) but can also include components from old products used in a new product.
Life cycle assessment (LCA)
LCA is a technique to assess the environmental aspects and potential impacts associated with a product, process, or service. It is derived by compiling an inventory of relevant energy and material inputs and environmental releases and evaluating the potential environmental impacts associated with identified inputs and releases.
Lifetime
The lifetime is the total amount of time a product is in use, including potential reuse of the whole product. The lifetime can be increased by repair or maintenance.
Linear economy
A linear economy consists of ‘take, make, dispose’ industrial processes and associated lifestyles resulting in a depletion of finite reserves. Virgin materials are used to create products that end up in landfills or incinerators.

¹ Methodology - An Approach to Measuring Circularity, Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Granta Design (2015)

Linear flow

The linear part of the material flow of a product is the part that comes from virgin materials and ends up as landfill (or energy recovery).

Material Circularity Indicator

The main indicator developed in this methodology. It assigns a score between 0 and 1 to a product (or company) assessing how restorative or linear the flow of the materials for the product (or the company's products) and how long and intensely the product (or the company's products) is used compared to similar industry-average products.

Recycling

Recycling is the process of recovering materials for the original purpose or for other purposes. The materials recovered feed back into the process as crude feedstock. Recycling excludes energy recovery.

Refurbishment

Refurbishment is the process of returning a product to good working condition by replacing or repairing major components that are faulty or close to failure and making cosmetic changes to update the appearance of a product, such as changing fabric or painting.

Remanufacture

Remanufacture denotes the process of disassembly and recovery at the sub-assembly or component level. Functioning, reusable parts are taken out of a used product and rebuilt into a new one. This process includes quality assurance and potential enhancements or changes to the components.

Reuse

To reuse a product is to reintroduce it for the same purpose and in its original form, following minimal maintenance and cosmetic cleaning. Within this methodology, this is considered via an increase of the product's utility (lifetime or functional units). If a product cannot be reused as a whole, individual components can be reused in a functional way. Within this methodology this is considered through the fraction F of the mass of feedstock for the product from reused sources and the fraction C of mass of the product going into component reuse.

Technical cycles

In technical cycles, products, components and materials are restored into the market at the highest possible quality and for as long as possible, through repair and maintenance, reuse, refurbishment, remanufacture, and ultimately recycling. The total mass flow for a product is derived as the sum of the amounts of material flowing in a linear and a restorative fashion.

Unrecovered waste

Unrecoverable waste includes waste going to landfill, waste to energy and any other type of process after the use of a product where the materials are no longer recoverable. Upcycling denotes a process of converting materials into new materials of higher quality and increased functionality.

Use phase

The use phase of a product starts when it reaches its first users and ends when it is not reused any more as a whole. After the use phase, components can be reused and the rest of the product can go into recycling, energy recovery or landfill.

Utility

The utility of a product measures how long and intensely it is used compared to an average product of the same type. The utility is derived from the lifetime and functional units of a product (compared to an industry-average product of the same type). Virgin material that has not been previously used or consumed, or subjected to processing other than for its original production.

1 Executive Summary

The main objective of this deliverable is to support the adoption of *product design for the circular economy* by European manufacturing organizations (including composite manufacturers) in the early stages of design, notably addressing design for modularity, durability, re-manufacturing and re-cycling through material and manufacturing process selection.

Together with the *Report on Baseline Description* (D1.1) and the *Design Circular: strategies and tools* (D2.2), this deliverable brings a review of the EcoBulk consortia knowledge of the methodology for the products design for the circular economy. The review provided is a mix of i) information and data collected from partners for product use cases, ii) assessment of tools developed by Granta, iii) reference databases, and iv) literature. The information reported in the deliverable represents the benchmark for the selection of materials and processes most suitable for the re-design of the products/components in the context of design methodology developed for the circular economy (WP3 and WP4).

Our aim is to assist product development by minimizing the environmental impact across the product life cycle (material production, product manufacture, transport, product use and end-of-life). To do so we present in the following chapters a Methodology for materials selection, a Circularity Audit approach and design tools to guide the material selection and the environmental awareness, namely:

- ❖ An Eco Audit Tool² introduced as an early stage product development tool;
- ❖ A Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)³ introduced as a mean to analyse how closed the product mass flow is, from a resource efficiency perspective.

A case study (CAR DASHBOARD) is used to describe the methodology. Please note that full details of the data used and of the analysis conducted are reported in the Appendix.

Further improvements to the social and environmental aspects are expected in the WP7 *Life Cycle Thinking*.

² <https://www.grantadesign.com/products/ecoaudit/>

³ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/programmes/insight/circularity-indicators>

2 Introduction: the material's life-cycle⁴

The study of a product and its associated material life cycle involves assessing the environmental impacts associated with its life, from the extraction of raw materials to their return to the ecosphere as waste-from “cradle to grave”. That means tracking materials through their life. The Figure 1 below is proposed as a sketch of the materials life cycle. Ore and feedstock, most of them non-renewable, are processed to give materials; these are manufactured into products that are used, and, at the end of their lives, disposed, a fraction perhaps entering a recycling loop, the rest committed to incineration or land-fill. Energy and materials are consumed at each point in this cycle (“phases”), with an associated penalty of CO₂ and other emissions (heat, and gaseous, liquid, and solid waste). The problem is that the sum of these unwanted by-products now often exceeds the capacity of the environment to absorb them. Sustainability and circular economy approaches require solutions of a completely different kind.

Figure 1 The material life-cycle [4]

In a circular economy model, materials circulate in material cycles. These cycles operate according to several conditions⁵. Organic materials follow a different reuse process than synthetic or technical materials. Because of this, it is important to ensure the separation of biological and technical materials after use, so they can each follow a separate reuse process (see Figure 2):

- **Technical materials**, such as fossil fuels, plastics, composites and metals are finite and cannot be renewed. In the techno-cycle it is important that the finite stock of materials is properly managed. ‘Using’ materials replaces the ‘consumption’. By focusing on value retention, materials are recovered from residual streams after use.
- **Organic materials**, such as cotton, food and water, can be taken up in the ecosystem by means of biological processes. In the bio-cycle it is important to ensure that the ecosystem and biological processes are enabled to function properly. Consumption may take place in this cycle (food, water, fertilizer) as

⁴ M.F. Ashby, A. Miller, F. Rutter, C. Seymour, and U.G.K Wegst “CES EduPack for Eco Design —A White Paper”, Version 5.1 © January 2012, Granta Design Ltd, Cambridge CB1 7EG, UK

⁵ TOWARDS A CIRCULAR ECONOMY: BUSINESS RATIONALE FOR AN ACCELERATED TRANSITION, Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Dec. 2015

long as the materials flows are not contaminated with toxic substances and ecosystems are not overloaded. When the ecosystem is balanced, organic materials are renewable.

Figure 2 The Butterfly Diagram describing circular material flows (Ellen Mac Arthur Foundation) [5]

Within the techno-cycle there are different levels of re-use:

1. **Repair and maintenance:** Restoring products during use to extend the lifespan of products
2. **Reuse and Redistribution:** Direct reuse through product reuse or sales.
3. **Refurbish & Remanufacture:** The thorough renovation and repair of product by the manufacturer.
4. **Recycle:** Parts or materials are recovered from the product to use them again

Most policy attention in the EU has been given to improving material and energy efficiency and on recycling of different types of waste, with initiatives such as the Ecodesign Directive (EC, 2009), product environmental footprints (PEFs) and eco-labelling explicitly targeting product-related aspects. However, reuse, repair, redistribution, remanufacture and refurbishment — the product-related inner circles of the circular economy — have received less attention, and strategies for widespread introduction of these concepts are less mature. Nonetheless, they potentially offer significant environmental benefits through keeping the value of products and materials in the economy⁶.

⁶ Circular by design Products in the circular economy, EEA Report No 6/2017

Material performance and trust in the safety of the materials are also relevant prerequisites for circularity. Clean materials are crucial for maintaining material performance and quality in recycling processes. Material performance and trust in the safety of the materials — in addition to the price — will largely determine whether or not consumers will buy recycled materials and derived products. Keeping material cycles clean is therefore essential for the circular economy, from both a safety and an economic point of view. This is a main area of potential synergy with EU chemicals legislation (for example REACH , EU, 2006) and the strategy for a non-toxic environment stipulated in the 7th EAP.

The choice of materials and processes influences all phases of Figure 1: production, through the drainage of resources and the undesired by-products of refinement; manufacture, through the level of efficiency and cleanness of the shaping, joining, and finishing processes; use, through the ability to conserve energy through light-weight design, higher thermal efficiency and lower energy drainage; and (finally) disposal through a greater ability to allow disassembly and recycling. Our aim is to assist the early design of the EcoBulk products in minimizing the undesired consequences of the four phases.

3 Methodology for materials selection in design⁷

The essential steps in the design process are described in the flow chart of Figure 3 (Cross, 2000; French 1985; Pahl and Beitz, 1997; Ullman, 1992; Ulrich and Eppinger, 1995). The design flow-chart shows the progression from identifying the business need, generation of concept designs, embodiment of design information, and detailed design. On the left and on the right: the design tools that support the process. A market need is identified and concepts to fill it are critically reviewed. Promising concepts pass to the embodiment stage, where the most suitable is selected for detailed design. The output is a product specification, enabling prototyping, testing, and the establishment of full production (manufacture and use).

Figure 3 Essential steps in the design process (courtesy Granta Design)

It is well accepted that 80% of environmental and economic life-cycle impacts of a product are decided at the Concept Design phase, and 90% by the time a prototype is manufactured. This is the point in the design at which materials and manufacturing processes are selected. These first two phases of the product life cycle typically dictate the major impacts of the remaining three life cycle phases: transport, use and end-of-life. In a typical product life cycle, environmental is typically left to Product Stewardship, after the product is manufactured. The Concept design phase, and specifically materials and manufacturing process selection for

⁷ Ashby, M.F. (2013) "Materials and the Environment—eco-informed material choice", 2nd edition

circular design are the focus of the remainder for this section. Examples of material and manufacturing process selection decisions which improve the environmental impact of the product life cycle include:

- Material: Minimize material in the part and embodied energy, raise the recycling percentage
- Manufacture: Minimize process energy and CO₂/kg
- Transport: Minimize distance moved, and select the transport mode with the lowest impact
- Use: Minimize mass and thermal/electrical loss
- End-of-life: select non-toxic materials and recyclable materials; consider disassembly

A methodology proposed by Mike Ashby for material and process selection is shared here [7]. A material is defined through its attributes: its density, strength, cost, resistance to corrosion, etc.... A design demands a certain profile of these: a low density, a high strength, a modest cost and resistance to sea water, perhaps. The task of selection is that of matching the choice of material to the requirements of the design.

Figure 4 Matching the choice of material to the requirements of the design

Efficient selection involves four steps, which we call here translation, screening, ranking, and supporting information.

Figure 5 The four main steps of the strategy for materials selection (Ashby 2013)

We provide here a description of how these steps are implemented to select materials and processes. (Dieter, 1991; Charles et al, 1997; Budinski and Budinski,1999; Farag, 1989; Lewis, 1990; Ashby, 2013).

Translation

The first task is that of translation: converting the business requirements into design requirements, and a prescription for selecting a material and a process to shape it. Any engineering component has one or more functions: to support a load, to contain a pressure, to transmit heat, and so forth. This must be achieved subject to constraints: that certain dimensions are fixed, that the component must carry the design loads without failure, that it insulates or conducts, that it can function in a certain range of temperature and in a given environment, and many more. In designing the component, the designer has one or more objectives: to make it as cheap as possible, perhaps, or as light, or as safe, or perhaps some combination of these. Certain parameters can be adjusted to optimize the objective – the designer is free to vary dimensions that are not constrained by design requirements and, most importantly, free to choose the material for the component. We refer to these as free variables. Function, constraints, objectives and free variables (Figure 6) define the boundary conditions for selecting a material and – in the case of load-bearing components – a shape for its cross-section. The first step in relating design requirements to material properties is a clear statement of function, constraints, objectives and free variables.

Function	What does the component do?
Constraints	What non-negotiable conditions must be met?
Objective	What is to be maximized/minimized?
Free variables	What parameters is the designer free to change?

Figure 6 Function, constraints, objectives and free variables (Ashby 2013)

Common constraints are:

“Must be” • Electrically conducting • Optically transparent • Corrosion resistant • Non-toxic • Non-restricted substance • Able to be recycled • Biodegradable

“Must meet a target value of” • Stiffness • Strength • Fracture toughness • Thermal conductivity • Service temperature

Common objectives are:

“Minimize” • Cost • Mass • Volume • Thermal losses • Electrical losses • Resource depletion • Energy consumption • Carbon emissions • Waste • Environmental impact • Water use

Screening: constraints as attribute limits

Unbiased selection requires that all materials are considered to be candidates until shown to be otherwise. The screening phase eliminates candidates that cannot “do the job” at all because one or more of their attributes lies outside the limits set by the constraints. As examples, the requirement that “the component must function in boiling water”, or that “the component must be transparent” imposes obvious limits on the attributes of maximum service temperature and optical transparency that successful candidates must meet. We refer to these as attribute limits.

Ranking: objectives expressed as material indices

To rank the materials that survive the screening step we need optimization criteria. They are found in material indices. A material index measures how well a candidate that has passed the screening steps can perform, that is, meet the objective. Performance is sometimes limited by a single property, sometimes by a combination of them. Thus the best materials for buoyancy are those with the lowest density, ρ ; those best for thermal insulation the ones with the smallest values of the thermal conductivity, λ , provided, of course, that they also meet all other constraints imposed by the design. Here maximizing or minimizing a single property maximizes performance. Often it is not one, but a group of properties that are relevant. Thus the best materials for a light stiff tie-rod are those with the smallest value of the group, ρ/E , where E is Young’s modulus. Those for a strong beam of lowest embodied energy are those with the lowest value of $H_m \rho / \sigma_y^{2/3}$ where H_m is the embodied energy of the material and σ_y is its yield strength. The property or property-group that maximizes performance for a given design is called its material index. There are many such indices, each associated with maximizing some aspect of performance. They provide criteria of excellence that allow ranking of materials by their ability to perform well in the given application.

To summarize:

In the translation step the design requirements are reformulated as constraints on material properties and process attributes and as one or more objectives: minimization of cost, or of weight, or of environmental impact, for instance. In screening, these constraints are used to eliminate materials that cannot meet the requirements. Screening may be performed in a digitized materials database containing material attributes (values for physical, mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties) and attributes relating to the environmental impact of the production of the material itself (its energy content, the greenhouse and acidification gases created by its production, its toxicity, and so forth). The design requirement that “the service temperature of a candidate material must be greater than 250C” imposes the limit that the maximum service temperature of any viable candidate must be greater than this; the design requirement of “electrical insulation” imposes a limit on electrical resistivity, and so forth. Attribute limits do not, however, provide any level of performance optimization. Ranking is achieved by the use of material indices derived from the objective mentioned above. These are groupings of material properties that characterize performance: the

materials with the largest values of an index maximize some aspect of performance. The specific stiffness, E/ρ , is one such index (E is Young's modulus and ρ the density); the specific strength $\rho\sigma/\gamma$ is another (γ is the yield strength). There are many material indices, each measuring some aspect of efficiency for a given function (Figure 7); a catalogue, with derivations, can be found in Ashby (2005). To deal with environmental impact at the production phase properly (Figure 8) we must seek to minimize the energy, the CO₂ burden or the eco-indicator value per unit of function. To select materials with the lowest eco-impact per unit of function we make use of performance indices that include energy content, CO₂ burden or eco-indicator.

	Configuration	Minimize volume	Minimize mass	Minimize embodied energy	Minimize material cost
Stiffness-limited Design	Tie	$1/E$	ρ/E	$H_m\rho/E$	$C_m\rho/E$
	Beam	$1/\sqrt{E}$	ρ/\sqrt{E}	$H_m\rho/\sqrt{E}$	$C_m\rho/\sqrt{E}$
	Panel	$1/\sqrt[3]{E}$	$\rho/\sqrt[3]{E}$	$H_m\rho/\sqrt[3]{E}$	$C_m\rho/\sqrt[3]{E}$
Strength-limited Design	Tie	$1/\sigma_0$	ρ/σ_0	$H_m\rho/\sigma_0$	$C_m\rho/\sigma_0$
	Beam	$1/\sigma_0^{2/3}$	$\rho/\sigma_0^{2/3}$	$H_m\rho/\sigma_0^{2/3}$	$C_m\rho/\sigma_0^{2/3}$
	Panel	$1/\sqrt{\sigma_0}$	$\rho/\sqrt{\sigma_0}$	$H_m\rho/\sqrt{\sigma_0}$	$C_m\rho/\sqrt{\sigma_0}$

Figure 7 Examples of indices for stiffness and strength-limited design (Ashby 2013)

Function	MAXIMIZE*
Minimum energy content for given tensile stiffness	$E/H_m\rho$
Minimum CO ₂ emissions for given tensile strength	$\sigma_y/[CO_2]\rho$
Minimum energy for given bending stiffness (beam)	$E^{1/2}/H_m\rho$
Minimum energy for given bending stiffness (panel)	$E^{1/3}/H_m\rho$
Minimum CO ₂ for given bending strength (beam)	$\sigma_f^{2/3}/[CO_2]\rho$
Minimum CO ₂ for given bending strength (panel)	$\sigma_f^{1/2}/[CO_2]\rho$
Minimum eco-indicator points for given thermal conduction	$\lambda/I_e\rho$

* H_m = embodied energy content per kg;
 $[CO_2]$ = CO₂ production / kg;
 I_e = eco-indicator / kg;
 E = Young's modulus;
 σ_{ts} = tensile strength;
 ρ = density.

Figure 8 Examples of indices to minimize impact in the production phase (Ashby 2013)

Indices can be used with material selection charts. These are plots of one material property or a combination of material properties against another shown schematically in Figure 9. Material indices can be plotted on a material selection chart, identifying materials that have attractive values of the index. The procedure⁸ allows

⁸ Used in ways detailed in Ashby (2013), available with the CES Selector and CES Edupack software solutions by Granta Design

ranking of materials according to cost per unit of function, mass per unit of function or, as described below, environmental impact per unit of function.

Figure 9 A selection chart for strength at minimum embodied energy, Ashby (2013)

Documentation

The output of the screening and ranking steps is a ranked short-list of candidates that meet the constraints and that satisfy the quantifiable requirements of the design. To proceed further we seek a detailed profile of each: its documentation. Typically, it is descriptive, graphical or pictorial: case studies of previous uses of the material, details of its corrosion behaviour in particular environments, of its availability and pricing, warnings of its environmental impact. Such information is found in handbooks, suppliers' data sheets, CD-based data sources and high quality Web sites. Documentation helps narrow the short-list to a final choice, allowing a definitive match to be made between design requirements and material attributes.

3.1 Eco-informed Material Selection: Eco-data and Eco-indicators for engineering materials

When selecting materials, in research and industrial product development, a number of Eco-Data needs to be taken into account. We provide below a list of Eco-Data used in the Ashby methodology.

Geo-economic data (information about the resource base from which the material is drawn and the rate at which it is being exploited):

- Annual world production (tonnes/yr) - the mass of the material extracted annually from ores or feedstock.
- Reserves (tonnes) - estimates of today's known economically recoverable ores or feedstock from which the material is extracted or created
- Typical exploited ore grade (%) - range of concentrations of currently-mined reserves
- Minimum economic ore grade (%) - measure of where extraction cost and market value come into balance
- Abundance in earth's crust (ppm) and abundance in sea water (ppm) - indicators of the limits that technology might sooner or later address

Material production (in terms of energy and emissions):

- Production energy (MJ/kg) - energy consumed in the four phases of Figure 1
- CO₂ creation (kg/kg)
- NO_x creation (kg/kg)
- SO_x creation (kg/kg)

The fossil-fuel energy consumed in making one kilogram of material is called its *embodied energy*. Some of the energy is stored in the created material and can be reused, in one sense or another, at the end of life. Polymers made from oil (as most are) contain energy in another sense—that of the oil that enters the production as a primary feedstock. Natural materials such as wood, similarly, contain “*intrinsic*” or “*contained*” energy, this time derived from solar radiation absorbed during growth. Views differ on whether the intrinsic energy should be included in the embodied energy or not. There is a sense in which not only polymers and woods, but also metals, carry intrinsic energy that could—by chemical reaction or by burning the metal in the form of finely-divided powder—be recovered, so omitting it when reporting embodied energy for polymers but including it for metals seems inconsistent. For this reason, we include intrinsic energy from non-renewable resources in reporting production energies, which generally lie in the range 50–500 MJ/kg. The existence of intrinsic energy has another consequence: that the energy to recycle a material is sometimes much less than that required for its first production, because the intrinsic energy is retained. The recycling energy is a useful indicator of the viability of recycling. Typical values lie in the range 10–100 MJ/kg. The production of 1 kg of material is associated with undesired gas emissions, among which CO₂, NO_x, SO_x and CH₄ cause general concern (global warming, acidification, ozone-layer depletion). The quantities can be large—each kg of aluminum produced by using energy from fossil fuels creates some 9 kg of CO₂, 40 grams of NO_x and 90 grams of SO_x. Production is generally associated with other undesirable outputs, particularly toxic wastes and particulates, but these can, in principle, be dealt with at source. Wood, bamboo, and other plant-based materials, too, contain intrinsic energy, but unlike man-made materials it derives from sunlight, not from non-renewable resources. The embodied energy data for these materials does not include this intrinsic energy, and the emissions take account the CO₂ absorbed during their growth.

Material processing energy at 30% efficiency

Many processes depend on casting, evaporation, or deformation. It is helpful to have a feel for the approximate magnitudes of energies required by these:

- Minimum energy to melt (MJ/kg)
- Minimum energy to vaporise (MJ/kg)
- Minimum energy to deform 90% (MJ/kg)

End of life

- Recycle (yes/no)
- Down-cycle (yes/no)
- Biodegrade (yes/no)
- Incinerate (yes/no)
- Landfill (yes/no)
- Recycling energy (MJ/kg)
- Recycle as fraction of current supply (%)

The fraction of a material production that can ultimately re-enter the cycle of Figure 1 depends both on the material itself and on the product into which has been incorporated.

Bio-data

Some materials are toxic, creating potential problems during production, during use, and during disposal:

- Toxicity rating (non-toxic, slightly toxic, toxic, very toxic)
- Approved for skin and food contact (yes/no)

Sustainability

- A renewable resource (yes/no) - an indication of whether or not the material derives from a renewable resource

Aggregated measures: Eco Indicators

- Eco-indicator 95
- Eco-indicator 99
- EPS value

To help designers to make decisions efforts have been made to condense the eco-information about a material into a single measure or indicator, giving the designer a simple, numeric ranking.

To do this, four steps are necessary, shown in Figure 10. The first is that of classification of the eco-data according to the impact each causes (global warming, ozone depletion, acidification etc.). The second step is that of normalization to remove the units and reduce them to a common scale (0-100, for instance). The third step is that of weighting to reflect the perceived seriousness of each impact, based on the classification of Step 1: thus global warming might be seen as more serious than resource depletion, giving it a larger weight. In the final step, the weighted, normalized measures are summed to give the indicator⁹.

⁹ Details can be found in EPS (1993), Idemat (1997), EDIP (1998), and Wenzel et al (1997).

Figure 10 The steps in calculating an eco-indicator (Ashby 2013)

Rational selection is typically a two-stage process in which we must first ask— which phase of the life cycle of the product under consideration makes the largest impact on the environment? The answer guides (Figure 11) the effective use of the data in substituting of selecting materials.

Figure 11 Rational use of the eco data starts with an analysis of the phase of life to be targeted (Ashby 2013)

3.2 Circularity Audit approach

In an open loop, materials used as feedstock (raw materials or input) to the manufacturing of a product are of one kind: *virgin material*. The post-consumer material is disposed into landfill and classified as *unrecoverable waste*. Closing loops of material flows is central to Circular Economy. A closed material loop refers to the approach to sustainably manage the materials used in a product, where the post-consumer material can become a feedstock via different routes (Figure 12):

- Reuse (no waste)
- Remanufacture (Refurbishing/upgrading)
- Recycling/Downcycling
- Or, possibly, Transformation via biochemical processes (not shown)

Figure 12 Product life-cycle phases of an Eco Audit in the context of a cradle-to-cradle model

Scenarios of circular economy can be analysed in terms of loops or lives that are studied individually starting with the first life of a product and subsequently various cases of additional life-cycle loops. These loops can be analysed in terms of mass flow, energy use, carbon emissions, environmental impacts or cost.

Reuse is considered reintroducing a product for the same or another purpose in its original form, following minimal maintenance and cosmetic cleaning. If a product cannot be reused as a whole, individual components can be reused in a functional way. In this case, the total life-cycle energy and CO₂ Footprint of the product comes mainly from the use phase but there may be transport energy and carbon emissions associated with the transcendence into the next product life. The total cost of the product equals the second hand price, including possible transport costs.

Remanufacture is the process of disassembly and returning a product to a good working condition by using new material and/or functioning, reusable parts taken out of used products. This process includes quality assurance and potential enhancements or changes to the components of the product. In the remanufacture case, the total life-cycle energy and carbon arising from processes involved in replacing or repairing parts, in addition to the use phase and transport energy and carbon emissions, are taken into account. The cost of the product should also include these additional contributions.

Recycling is the process of recovering materials for the original purpose or for other purposes. The recovered materials feed back into the process as crude feedstock. In this case, the total lifecycle impacts should take into account the energy and carbon emissions derived from any additional recycling processes involved, as well as additional costs.

The analysis of the life cycle of a product and assessment of the eco-impact it creates will be explored in WP7 using the techniques of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). This will require information of the life-history of the

product at a level of precision that is only available after the product has been produced. LCA is a product assessment tool, not a design tool. The tool will be used in Ecobulk for the evaluation and comparison of the existing products with the new ones. The difficulty at the current stage of project is that decisions taken in the early stage of the design lead to commitments that cannot easily be changed later. For this reason the need is for tools to exploits the information available early in the design process—the “concept” and “embodiment” stages of Figure 3. It should be flexible enough to accommodate future refinement and simple enough to allow rapid “What-if” exploration of alternatives.

To fulfil this purpose, we present, in the following chapters, two design tools to guide the environmental awareness in the current early design process:

- ❖ An **Eco Audit Tool** introduced as an early stage product development tool
- ❖ A **Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)** that allows quantitative assessment of the circularity of a product and the tracking of progress towards more circular design, introduced as a mean to analyse how closed the product mass flow is, from a resource efficiency perspective.

The approach used in the Eco Audit tool has three components:

1. **Adopt simple measures of environmental stress.** The use of energy or CO₂ footprint for measuring environmental stress, rather than combined indicators. Energy has the merit that it is the easiest to monitor, can be measured with relative precision and, with appropriate precautions, can when needed be used as a proxy for CO₂.
2. **Distinguish the phases of life.** Breakdown, assigning a fraction of the total life-energy demands of a product to material production, product manufacture, transport, and product use and disposal. Product disposal can take many different forms, some carrying an energy penalty, some allowing energy recycling or recovery.
3. **Base the subsequent action on the energy or carbon breakdown.** If material production is the dominant phase, then minimizing the mass of material used and choosing materials with low embodied energy could be logical ways forward. If manufacture is an important energy-using phase of life, reducing processing energies becomes the prime target. If transport makes a large contribution, then seeking a more efficient transport mode or reducing distance becomes the first priority. When the use phase dominates the strategy is that of minimizing mass (if the product is part of a system that moves), or increasing thermal efficiency (if a thermal or thermo-mechanical system), or reducing electrical losses (if an electro-mechanical system). In general, the best material choice to minimize one phase will not be the one that minimizes the others, requiring trade-off methods to guide the choice.

The Eco Audit approach provides a basic life cycle assessment. A complementary and more qualitative approach to deal scenarios that include lifetime extension and remanufacturing (i.e. focusing on product integrity instead of material cycling) is provided in Deliverable 2.2.

4 Material and Process Selection Tools

4.1 MI: Explore

MI:Explore¹⁰ is a web application that can be customized for specific users, helping them find, visualize and apply materials and process information quickly. MI:Explore will be configured for the MI EcoBulk Database enabling the benchmarking of materials and processes options. Benchmarking is done visually, using property charts that are prepared quickly based on a chosen set of properties or attributes (constraints and objectives). With MI:Explore is possible to identify the materials and processes that meet the product requirements and study the trade-off between different objectives. This enables an informed selection based on the widest range of available information, while maintaining traceability to facilitate critical discussions about decisions.

We provide in Figure 13, as an example, the MI Explore configured for Granta MaterialUniverse™ (a database containing nearly 4,000 records providing properties for virtually every type of purchasable engineering material).

Figure 13 MI Explore user interface

Configurations

GRANTA MI can support multiple configurations of MI:Explore. Each configuration can serve up a particular subset of data, a particular search template, and a configurable set of pre-defined reports. Examples of configurations relevant to EcoBulk are:

- * A configuration to help users select materials and processes, with the ability to search by properties or attributes (ex. mechanical properties), and the ability to display the results as a list or on bubble charts
- * A configuration to report on regular QA batch testing of materials, where the user can choose a material and date range, and plot any measured property against time.

¹⁰ MI:Explore , Granta Design Limited, Cambridge, UK, 2017 (www.grantadesign.com)

* Enabling simulation engineers to examine material curve data, select material models and output a CAE material card deck, while retaining the benefits of central management of this resource

Figure 14 MI Explore configurations

Searching and selecting attribute limits

MI:Explore provides an intuitive search pane based on a set of properties or attributes chosen for that particular MI:Explore configuration. Numerical properties (ex. price, density) appear as slider bars which can be dragged interactively or set to specific values for fine tuning. Discrete properties (ex. material family, filler/reinforcement) and linked data appear in the search pane as intuitive drop-down menus. Textual properties appear as search boxes. The search is interactive – as the user adjusts sliders or picks options, the resulting reports are updated dynamically.

Figure 15 MI Explore search pane and attribute limits selection

Ranking and Selecting

MI:Explore displays the results of searches and attribute limits selection:

- * A List View which summarizes all the records associated with the configuration which pass the search criteria. Users can add columns interactively to the list view – to build up tabular comparison reports of results. For example, a user might have searched for materials with a given strength, but might add price and density columns to their comparison table to understand the trade-offs associated with the results.
- * A Thumbnails View which displays results as images – such as micrographs, process schematics, surface treatment textures, colors, example application photos, etc.
- * A Chart View which displays results as bubble plots. The user can choose which properties to display on the axes, and choose linear or logarithmic scales.
- * Curves view, for example to show and compare Tensile Response curves and read off point values

Figure 16 MI Explore ranking and selection

Figure 17 MI Explore datasheets

Reports, Datasheets and Editing

All the results pages described above are interactive. Clicking a result opens a 'mini datasheet', showing additional properties of the material or process chosen for that MI:Explore configuration.

MI:Explore can also be configured to support new record creation, hence the addition of new materials, process or tests data. The placement of newly created records can be set in the configuration.

5 Design and Circularity Tools

5.1 MI:BoM Analyser and Eco Audit

GRANTA MI:BoM Analyser¹¹ is a tool developed by Granta Design for Engineers, Designers and Legislative compliance. The tool Support the analyses of products from the Bill of Materials (BoMs) helping in reducing business risks by design, design for circular economy and closed loop remanufacturing.

Examples of design strategies for reducing the risks may be:

- ✓ Reduce **environmental impact** by material substitution or increasing Material Circularity
- ✓ Reducing **restricted substances** content by material substitution
- ✓ Increase **Material Circularity** by investigating remanufacturing business model

Materials and processes from the GRANTA MI database can be assigned to parts in the BoM. The tool can be used at various stage of the design process, from preliminary BoM (investigating new design strategies), to detailed BoM (supporting design for compliance) by inputting BoM data from dedicated interface, excel template, PLM systems and CAD/CAE supported software (Figure 18).

Figure 18 MI BoM Analyser model

Through the use of BoM Analyser is possible to run analysis reports like Eco-audit Assessment for single and multiple use cycles, Circularity indicator, Restricted Substance risks, evaluation of supply chain disruption risks such as monopoly risk, conflict minerals, price volatility etc.

¹¹ MI:BoM Analyser , Granta Design Limited, Cambridge, UK, 2017 (www.grantadesign.com)

The **Eco-Audit** tool in particular can help visualize the four-cycle phases (plus transport) and estimate eco-properties using assumptions and models detailed in the software.

The tool provides an estimate of the environmental impact of a product in terms of energy use and CO₂ footprint, and enables to identify which phase of the product lifecycle has the greatest impact, so that the designer can focus the design efforts in areas that will lead to the greatest improvement in environmental performance. The product is specified through a Bill of Materials (BoM). The output is given visually in a Summary chart for CO₂ footprint and Energy.

Figure 19 Eco-Audit model

The tool can be used to analyse and report on a single design, or to compare two alternative designs. The analysis calculates the energy use and CO₂ footprint associated with five phases of the product lifecycle: material production, manufacturing, transport, product use, and disposal/end of first life (Figure 19).

Material production

There are three main contributors to the embodied energy and CO₂ footprint of the Material Phase. These are: the embodied energy of the raw material, the energy associated with collecting the manufacturing waste and the 'credit' for recovering the manufacturing waste. For recycling, which is the default option for reclaiming the manufacturing waste, the credit for recovery is calculated. In cases where a material is flagged as not recyclable, it is assumed that it will be downcycled, where it will be either reprocessed or comminuted into aggregate. As the mass specified in the bill of materials (BoM) represents that of the finished component, there is a need to 'correct' its value to account for material that is removed by the secondary machining processes. This influences the environmental footprint of both the material and manufacturing life phases. To account for this, both the amount of 'starting' material and the waste produced need to be known. These are calculated by applying 'correction' factors to the final component mass.

Manufacturing

The manufacturing phase calculations can be split into two groups; primary & secondary processes (which are applied to individual materials/components) and, joining and finishing processes (which are independent of materials/components). There are two contributions to the manufacturing phase for an individual

component. The energy and CO₂ footprint associated with the primary process (based on the initial amount of material used) and the secondary machining process (based on the amount of material removed).

Product Use

There are two different classes of contribution. Some products are (normally) static but require energy to function: electrically powered household or industrial products like hairdryers, electric kettles, refrigerators, power tools, and space heaters are examples. Even apparently non-powered products, like household furnishings or unheated buildings, still consume some energy in cleaning, lighting, and maintenance. The first class of contribution, then, relates to the power consumed by, or on behalf of, the product itself. The second class is associated with transport. Products that form part of a transport system add to its mass and so augment its energy consumption and CO₂ burden.

Disposal

This phase covers the energy or CO₂ footprint associated with collection of materials or components (and disposal in landfill, where applicable), and separation and sorting ready for processing. There are six options for disposal of products at the end of their first life:

- ❖ Landfill
- ❖ Combust for energy recovery
- ❖ Downcycle
- ❖ Recycle
- ❖ Re-condition or re-engineer
- ❖ Reuse as is

The first, landfill, is the least attractive. Combustion, properly carried out, recovers some of the embodied energy of the materials of the product, but the recovery-efficiency is low, the economics are unattractive and proposals to build combustion plants are often opposed by local residents. Recycling is the best way to extract value from waste and return materials to the supply-stream, preserving material stock. Re-conditioning or re-engineering restores used products or recoverable components to as-new condition, but establishing a market and maintaining a supply chain of recondition products is not easy, and issues of warranty and responsibility for malfunction are deterrents. Reuse sounds the most attractive option; passing products from consumers who no longer want them to those willing to accept them in a used state. This requires a market place where seller and buyer can meet and negotiate (like eBay®) and an acceptance of used products rather than new.

Transports

Transportation is an energy-conversion process: primary energy (oil) is converted into mechanical power and this is used to provide motion. As in any energy-conversion process there are losses, here most conveniently expressed as the energy dissipated per tonne per kilometer transported (MJ/tonne.km), carrying with it an associated CO₂ footprint (kg/tonne.km). Sea, ground and air transport systems usually burn hydrocarbon fuel, so the CO₂ emission is approximately proportional to the energy. Transport dissipates energy in two ways: as work against drag exerted by air or water, and as work to accelerate the vehicle, lost on braking. The tool retrieves the energy / tonne.km and the CO₂ / tonne.km for the chosen transport type from a look-up table and multiplies them by the product weight and the distance travelled, finally summing the stages.

The Eco Audit reports show energy use and CO₂ footprint values for each lifecycle phase (Figure 20), and the for the product lifecycle as a whole. The reports also show a breakdown of these values by part, so the parts in the Bill of Materials that contribute the most to the impact are easily identified. An 'End of life (EoL) Potential' is also calculated, representing the end of life savings or 'credits' that can be realized in future life cycles by using the recovered material or components.

Figure 20 Example of Eco Audit comparison diagram of impacts

One built-in features of the Eco Audit that results advantageous for the purpose of the EcoBulk product design is the 'Compare with' function that allows to easily introduce parallel scenarios into the bar charts. This can be used to compare alternative materials options and alternative product lives by changing the End-of-life option for a product manufactured from virgin material. Visualizing the life-cycle properties in parallel, adds a dimension to the chart that can be used to put impacts in perspective.

5.2 Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)

Circular economy metrics for product performance evaluation have been developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation and Granta Design in a collaboration funded by Life+. The Material Circularity Indicators Tool in particular has been developed by Granta Design, and integrated with the MI:Product Intelligence package. As a result, a new Circularity Report is available in BoM Analyser. The Circularity Report analyses environmental, regulatory and supply chain risks alongside the Material Circularity Indicator.

The product level Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) measures the extent to which a product has minimised the amount of virgin material as feedstock and unrecoverable waste at end of life, and also how long and intensely it is used compared to a similar one. The latter comparison with industry is because the longer a product is used, or if it is used at a more intense rate (for example a product shared vs bought per individual), the less materials is used over the same period of time. For more information on this indicators, background and theory of calculations, please see the paper available at Ellen MacArthur Foundation website¹².

MCI values range from 0 (zero) to 1. The higher the MCI score, the better the materials of the product circulate.

The equation for MCI_p of a product is:

$$MCI_p = 1 - \frac{V+W}{2M + \frac{W_F - W_C}{2}} \cdot F(X) \quad (1)$$

Where V is the fraction of feedstock from virgin sources, W is the unrecoverable waste calculated from the waste going to landfill, and also considers the average of waste generated in the recycling process W_C and the waste generated to produce any recycled content used as feedstock W_F . M is the product mass. F(X) denotes how the lifespan and intensity of the product compares with the industry average, and for our case study, we will indicating it is the same, hence $F(X) = 0.9$.

The definition used here for MCI_p focuses on the circulation of materials. In Deliverable 2.2 on the design framework, in addition attention is given to circulation of products and parts in order to maintain functionality.

¹² <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/programmes/insight/circularity-indicators>

6 Case study: CAR DASHBOARD

6.1 Product Description and Design Requirements

Table 1 captures the concept design information, and translates business needs to product technical attributes.

Sector / Application	Automotive / Internal finishing (Dashboard, Airbag, Radio, Aerators)	
Component / Shape	Car Dashboard / Complex 3D	
Materials	Reference materials: PC+ABS	
Component Description	Design (Note: <i>Image shown is Indicative only</i>)	
	Assembly method	Plastic clips, Metallic clips
	Finishing	Aesthetic (Mass coloured, Painted)
	Current lifespan (yrs)	5 - 7 years
	Current end of life	Downcycled (mixed plastics, plastics with coatings/paints)
Design requirements	Physical/Mechanical	Stiffness and impact resistance Heat ageing and light resistance. Fogging, odour and VOC. Colour fastness to wear by abrasion and rubbing (dry, soapy water, heptane, perspiration). Resistance to micro-organism in humid atmosphere. Chemical resistance (hand cream). Adhesion of paints and coatings.
	Max TOT Weight (kg)	0,24kg
	Processing	Injection Moulding.

Table 1 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Product Description and Design Requirements

We provide in *Appendix* the details of the Reference Materials.

6.2 Materials Trade-off and benchmarking with MI:Explore

The basis of the material selection for this case study is the data records for nearly 4000 engineering materials available in MaterialUniverse¹³. An overview of the subset *All bulk materials* is shown as an example in a modulus vs price chart below.

Figure 21 Example of All Bulk materials chart

These are not all candidates for the Car Dashboard. Considering the nature of the materials identified by the consortium as potential substitute, a starting point for the selection would be to consider all thermoplastics. These can be included selecting the material family from the search pane, as shown below. This removes the unsuitable materials mentioned above.

¹³ Granta MaterialUniverse™, Granta Design Limited, Cambridge, UK, 2017 (www.grantadesign.com)

Figure 22 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Thermoplastics subset materials chart

Constraints and objectives: we begin selection by screening the plastics against some of the key requirements for the product (e.g. strength, min and max service temperatures, resistance to water etc). The materials that pass these ‘attribute limits’, summarized below, appear interactively on the materials property chart making the final choice less exhausting.

The requirements considered for the product are:

- Price: max 3.1 €/kg (~4USD/kg)
- Young’s Modulus: min 2.2 GPa
- Tensile Strength: min 54 MPa
- Elongation: min 3 %strain
- Heat deflection temperature 0.45MPa: min 126 °C
- Heat deflection temperature 1.8MPa: min 106 °C
- Thermal expansion coefficient: min 0.7 μ strain/°C
- Optical/Aesthetic properties: Opaque
- Processing Properties: Injection molding=Acceptable/Excellent, Extrusion=Acceptable
- Durability: Water(fresh)=Acceptable/Excellent, UV Radiation=Fair/Good/Excellent
- End of Life: Recycle

Using the function of Explore is possible to add and compare the reference material and the potential substitutes in a ‘Collection’.

The resulting list of candidates (including the reference material) after materials are screened is shown below with some key attributes.

Name	Price (USD/kg)	Density (kg/m ³)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Yield strength (elastic limit) (MPa)
ABS+PC (injection molding and extrusion)	3.34 - 3.6	1070 - 1150	2.41 - 2.62	24.1 - 51
PA6 (40% mineral)	2.56 - 2.9	1460 - 1490	2.2 - 2.74	49 - 61.1
PC+PET (general purpose)	2.4 - 2.8	1200 - 1220	2.09 - 2.26	55 - 60
PC+PET (impact modified)	2.97 - 3.36	1200 - 1240	2 - 2.25	53 - 59
POM (copolymer, UV stabilized)	2.54 - 2.76	1400 - 1420	2.5 - 2.9	60.7 - 64
POM (homopolymer, UV stabilized)	3.02 - 3.17	1410 - 1430	2.76 - 3.1	65.7 - 72.4

Figure 23 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Materials trade-off (list)

We can see that there are different types of thermoplastics satisfying the selected requirements. Once more information has been obtained regarding the Ecobulk composite materials, a similar evaluation can be carried out taking the properties of these materials in account in addition to those of the thermoplastics.

Figure 24 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Materials trade-off (chart)

Some useful material property charts that can guide materials selection to minimize mass, material embodied energy and material carbon footprint are shown in the following Figures.

Figure 25 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Modulus-Density for stiffness at minimum weight

Figure 26 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Strength-Density for strength at minimum weight

Figure 27 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Modulus - Embodied Energy for stiffness at minimum embodied energy

Figure 28 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Strength - Embodied Energy for strength at minimum embodied energy

Figure 29 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Modulus – Carbon Footprint for stiffness at minimum carbon release

From the charts presented above we can do a first evaluation of the performances and environmental benefits associated with the material substitution. In particular the material POM (copolymer, UV stabilised) compared to the reference material is associated with lower embodied energy and carbon footprint. In the following chapters a more comprehensive analysis will be carried out to investigate the environmental impacts at product level.

6.3 Process selection with MI:Explore

The basis of the process selection for this case study is the data records available in ProcessUniverse¹⁴. An overview of the *All Shaping Processes subset* (including secondary processes) is shown as an example in a production rate vs range of section thickness chart below.

Figure 30 Example of All Process chart

As for the material benchmarking we begin selection by screening the processes against some of the key requirements for the product. The processes that pass these ‘attribute limits’, summarized below, appear interactively on the process property chart making the final choice less exhausting.

The process requirements considered for the product are:

- Shape: solid/hollow 3D
- Materials: Thermoplastics
- Range of section thickness: 2mm (max)
- Primary shaping process: Yes
- Labor intensity: Low/Medium
- Production rate: 60 units/hr (min)

Name	Solid 3-D	Mass range (kg)	Range of section thickness (mm)	Labor intensity	Production rate (units) (/hr)
Injection molding (thermoplastics)	Yes	0.01 - 25	0.4 - 6.3	low	60 - 3000
Reaction injection molding	Yes	0.5 - 300	2 - 150	medium	6 - 60

Figure 31 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Processes trade-off (list)

¹⁴ Granta ProcessUniverse™, Granta Design Limited, Cambridge, UK, 2017 (www.grantadesign.com)

Figure 32 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Process trade-off (chart)

As we can see from the figures above the best option to satisfy the production requirements of the Car Dashboard component is the injection molding process.

As reference we provide below a list of additional requirements that can be used for process selection.

Shape	Physical attributes	Economic Attributes	Cost modelling
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular prismatic, • Non-circular prismatic, • Flat sheet, • Dished sheet, • Solid 3-D, • Hollow 3-D 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass range (min) (kg), • Mass range (max) (kg), • Range of section thickness (min) (mm), • Range of section thickness (max) (mm), • Tolerance (min) (mm), • Tolerance (max) (mm), • Roughness (min) ($\text{\AA}\mu\text{m}$), • Roughness (max) ($\text{\AA}\mu\text{m}$), • Cutting speed (min) (m/s), • Cutting speed (max) (m/s), • Minimum cut width (min) (mm), • Minimum cut width (max) (mm) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic batch size (units) (min), • Economic batch size (units) (max), • Relative equipment cost, • Relative tooling cost, • Labor intensity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capital cost (min) (USD), • Capital cost (max) (USD), • Material utilization fraction (min), • Material utilization fraction (max), • Production rate (units) (min) (/hr), • Production rate (units) (max) (/hr), • Production rate (length) (min) (m/s), • Production rate (length) (max) (m/s), • Tool life (units) (min), • Tool life (units) (max), • Tool life (length) (min) (m), • Tool life (length) (max) (m), • Tooling cost (min) (USD), • Tooling cost (max) (USD)

Table 2 Example of Process requirements

6.4 Environmental impacts and material circularity

6.4.1 Eco Audit Analysis

In the Eco Audit, the four life-cycle phases are estimated using assumptions and models detailed in the software. Our approach is product-centered, rather than user-centered, and the product is specified through the **Bill of Materials (BoM)**¹⁵, as shown below (Table 3). We consider for simplicity the Concept design with POM having same mass of 0.20kg as the Baseline reference product.

Material	Baseline (kg)	Concept (kg)	Change (kg)
POM (copolymer, UV stabilized)		0.20	0.20
ABS+PC (injection molding and extrusion)	0.20		-0.20
Iron, commercial purity, ingot iron, hot rolled, >99.9%Fe	0.0010	0.0010	0.0
Total	0.20	0.20	0.0

Table 3 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Bill of Materials (comparison)

Depending on the material assigned to the part, we are able to choose from the following **end-of-life treatments** in Eco Audit Analysis:

- **Reuse:** The product is redistributed (intact) to a consumer sector that is willing to accept it in its used state, either for its original purpose or for a different one. Note: This end-of-life treatment refers to reuse of the product as a whole (as opposed to Re-engineer, in which individual components are recovered and reused).
- **Re-engineer:** At the end of the product's useful life, individual components are recovered, cleaned, inspected, repaired (if necessary), and reused in a new product or as a replacement part. (This is also called parts harvesting and remanufacturing). Note: This end-of-life treatment refers to the recovery and reuse of individual parts (as opposed to reuse of the product as a whole), so you can specify it independently for any part in the BoM.
- **Recycle:** The recovered material is reprocessed and returned to the supply chain as a material of similar type, with similar performance and embodied energy. (This is also called closed-loop recycling.) Typically used for metals and glasses.
- **Downcycle – reprocessing:** The recovered material is reprocessed and returned to the supply chain as a material with lower performance and lower embodied energy – for example, conversion of PET bottles into fibers for fleece clothing. This is also called open-loop recycling. Typically used for metals, thermoplastic polymers and thermoplastic elastomers (TPEs).
- **Downcycle - crushing, grinding, shredding:** The recovered material is reprocessed and returned to the supply chain as a material with lower performance and lower embodied energy, by crushing, grinding or shredding it into aggregate or filler replacement. (This is also called comminution. Typically used for ceramics and glasses, natural materials (organic & inorganic), thermoset plastics, and thermoset elastomers.
- **Downcycle - metal recovery:** Downcycling of electrical components by recovering their metal content, typically using evaporation and condensation processes. This is economically and environmentally worthwhile because it reduces the amount of toxic material entering landfill sites and reduces the need for mining of precious metals.

¹⁵ MI:BoM Analyser , Granta Design Limited, Cambridge, UK, 2017

- **Combustion:** Recovery of some of the embodied energy in the material by controlled combustion, capturing the heat released. This is often seen as the last stage in the downcycling cascade for organic-based materials. It is not generally suitable for materials with a Heat of combustion (net) value below 5 MJ/kg.
- **Landfill:** The part or material is committed to landfill, without any attempt to recover or reuse it.

In our case study we know the reference product is currently entirely downcycled (mixed plastic) so we will input this end of life options for its components. On the other hand we will consider the new concept design as recycled at the end of life. Re-use might be another option, although this would imply that a design solution must be found to reduce the level of degradation caused by UV radiation during the use phase.

The user-related parameters, such as mode of energy use, transport modes and distances, etc. are given as inputs:

Transport type = 14 tonne truck (estimated for the case study)

Transport distance = 100km (estimated for the case study)

Product lifetime = 7 years (given by manufacturer)

Product utility = industry average (used for circularity analysis)

The results of calculating energy, carbon emissions and costs for the Baseline product and the New Concept design are detailed in the Appendix, and graphically represented in the comparison Figure 34 and Figure 35. In Figure 33 below are summarised the overall benefits obtained with the material substitution.

Figure 33 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Eco Audit Comparison Overview

It can be seen in the Eco Audit results (following pictures) that the phase that dominates the energy use, and therefore the CO2 footprint, is the *Material production* rather than the *Manufacture* or *Use phase*. The POM substitution and the recycling options at end of life generate a decrease in energy use and CO2 footprint in both the material production and manufacture phases. On the other hand the results of the analysis show an increase in energy use and CO2 footprint in the *Disposal phase*. Overall the material substitution and the recycling end of life option chosen for the new design concept result in a 4% reduction in energy and 8% CO2 footprint (for the first life), corresponding to 50% and 46% total reductions (based on 7 years use) and 400% and 380% increase in end of life potential. 'End of life (EoL) Potential' represents the end of life savings or 'credits' that can be realized in future life cycles by using the recovered material or components.

 Energy usage: summary for 4 parts analyzed

	Baseline	New concept	Change	Percentage
Material (MJ)	22	22	-0.097	0 % reduction
Manufacture (MJ)	6.1	5.0	-1.1	18 % reduction
Transport (MJ)	0.017	0.017	0.0	0 % change
Use (MJ)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0 % change
Disposal (MJ)	0.10	0.14	0.041	40 % increase
Total (for first life) (MJ)	28	27	-1.1	4 % reduction
End of life potential (MJ)	-2.9	-14	-11	400 % increase
Total (MJ)	25	13	-13	50 % reduction

Figure 34 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Eco Audit Energy usage comparison

 CO2 footprint: summary for 4 parts analyzed

	Baseline	New concept	Change	Percentage
Material (kg)	0.99	0.96	-0.032	3 % reduction
Manufacture (kg)	0.46	0.38	-0.081	17 % reduction
Transport (kg)	0.0012	0.0012	0.0	0 % change
Use (kg)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0 % change
Disposal (kg)	0.0061	0.0086	0.0024	40 % increase
Total (for first life) (kg)	1.5	1.3	-0.11	8 % reduction
End of life potential (kg)	-0.13	-0.63	-0.50	380 % increase
Total (kg)	1.3	0.72	-0.61	46 % reduction

Figure 35 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Eco Audit CO2 Footprint comparison

6.4.2 Water usage, costs and REACH comparison

BoM Analyser allows comparison of other important factors influencing the decision making. These are: water usage, material cost, maximum price variation, REACH obligations, RoHS compliance, conflict material reporting risk, food-contact compatibility, and end-of-life treatments for parts. We provide below the results of *Water usage* comparison, used to compare the volume of water used in material production for two BoMs, *Cost comparison*, comparison of material costs for two BoMs, and *REACH Comparison*, comparison of restricted substance content for two products. The full reports are available in Appendix.

Figure 36 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Water usage, Costs and REACH Comparison Overview

The new concept design in our case study results in reduced material costs (31%) and reduced content (-1%) of restricted substances. However, we have an increase water usage (47%) that needs to be taken in consideration as part of the overall environmental assessment.

Water usage: summary for 4 parts analyzed

	Baseline	New concept	Change	Percentage
Material (liters)	36	52	17	47 % increase
Manufacture (liters)			Not included in analysis	
Transport (liters)			Not included in analysis	
Use (liters)			Not included in analysis	
Disposal (liters)			Not included in analysis	
End of life potential (liters)			Not included in analysis	

Figure 37 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Water usage comparison

 Cost: summary for 4 parts analyzed

	Baseline	New concept	Change	Percentage
Material (USD)	0.83	0.57	-0.26	31 % reduction
Manufacture (USD)			Not included in analysis	
Transport (USD)			Not included in analysis	
Use (USD)			Not included in analysis	
Disposal (USD)			Not included in analysis	
End of life potential (USD)			Not included in analysis	

Figure 38 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – Costs comparison

The REACH Comparison report lists any substance on the REACH Candidate List of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) that may be present in either or both of the assemblies, with its maximum % (by weight) in each assembly, and the change in its % (wt) between the baseline and concept.

Substance	CAS	Baseline wt% max	Concept wt% max	Change wt% max
Phenol, 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1,1-dimethylpropyl)-	25973-55-1	1.0 %	0.0 %	-1.0 %
Phenol, 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-6-(1-methylpropyl)-	36437-37-3	1.0 %	0.0 %	-1.0 %
Phenol, 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	3846-71-7	1.0 %	0.0 %	-1.0 %
Phenol, 2-(5-chloro-2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	3864-99-1	1.0 %	0.0 %	-1.0 %

Figure 39 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – REACH comparison

6.4.3 MCI calculations

The Material Circularity report can be used to analyse the extent to which a product's material usage maximises restorative flow, as represented by the Material Circularity indicator described in Chapter 5.2. The report includes complementary indicators that can be used to prioritize the adoption of circular practices, including: material price variation, REACH obligations, conflict material reporting risk, and RoHS compliance (risk indicators); and energy usage, CO2 footprint, and water usage (impact indicators).

The report analyses the Bill of Materials at three levels:

"Summary (Product level)": Shows indicator values for the product as a whole, corresponding to the highest level of the Bill of Materials. MCI values range from 0 (zero) to 1. The higher the MCI score, the better the materials of the product circulate. In our case study we obtain a higher Material Circularity indicator (MCI=0.40) in the new concept design, as shown below.

Material Circularity indicator (MCI) for the reference product:

0.10 out of 1

Material Circularity indicator (MCI) for the new concept design:

0.40 out of 1

Figure 40 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – MCI summary

"Initial breakdown": Shows indicator values for components (sub-assemblies or parts) that are immediately below the product level in the Bill of Materials hierarchy. Note that the indicator values shown at this level may be for a part that uses a single material, or for a sub-assembly consisting of multiple parts, each using a

different material. In our case study we obtain the following for the reference product and the new concept design:

Component name (sub-assembly or part)	Component type	Total mass of component in product (kg)	Quantity of component per product	% reused or recycled material per component				MCI
				Feedstock		Material collection		
				Reused FU	Recycled FR	Reused CU	Recycled CR	
Clips	Part	0.001	1	0%	0%	0%	100%	0.52
Garnish	Part	0.010	1	0%	0%	0%	0%	0.10
Additional Part	Part	0.026	1	0%	0%	0%	0%	0.10
Dashboard	Part	0.170	1	0%	0%	0%	0%	0.10

Component name (sub-assembly or part)	Component type	Total mass of component in product (kg)	Quantity of component per product	% reused or recycled material per component				MCI
				Feedstock		Material collection		
				Reused FU	Recycled FR	Reused CU	Recycled CR	
Clips	Part	0.001	1	0%	0%	0%	100%	0.52
Garnish	Part	0.010	1	0%	0%	0%	100%	0.40
Additional Part	Part	0.026	1	0%	0%	0%	100%	0.40
Dashboard	Part	0.170	1	0%	0%	0%	100%	0.40

Figure 41 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – MCI initial breakdown

“Full breakdown”: Shows indicator values for materials used in parts, at the lowest level possible in the Bill of Materials hierarchy. In our case study we obtain the following for the reference product and the new concept design:

Material	Total mass of part in product (kg)	Quantity of part per product	% reused or recycled material per part						MCI
			Feedstock			Material collection			
			Reused FU	Recycled FR	Recycling efficiency EF	Reused CU	Recycled CR	Recycling efficiency EC	
Iron, commercial purity, ingot iron, hot rolled, >99.9%Fe	0.001	1	0%	0%	0.90	0%	100%	0.90	0.52
ABS+PC (injection molding and extrusion)	0.010	1	0%	0%	0.40	0%	0%	0.40	0.10
ABS+PC (injection molding and extrusion)	0.026	1	0%	0%	0.40	0%	0%	0.40	0.10
ABS+PC (injection molding and extrusion)	0.170	1	0%	0%	0.40	0%	0%	0.40	0.10

Material	Total mass of part in product (kg)	Quantity of part per product	% reused or recycled material per part						MCI
			Feedstock			Material collection			
			Reused FU	Recycled FR	Recycling efficiency EF	Reused CU	Recycled CR	Recycling efficiency EC	
Iron, commercial purity, ingot iron, hot rolled, >99.9%Fe	0.001	1	0%	0%	0.90	0%	100%	0.90	0.52
POM (copolymer, UV stabilized)	0.010	1	0%	0%	0.60	0%	100%	0.60	0.40
POM (copolymer, UV stabilized)	0.026	1	0%	0%	0.60	0%	100%	0.60	0.40
POM (copolymer, UV stabilized)	0.170	1	0%	0%	0.60	0%	100%	0.60	0.40

Figure 42 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – MCI full breakdown

To be noted that the above calculations are made considering 0% of reused or recycled feedstock. Only at the end of life (collection) the product is considered recycled. The MCI values calculated can differ substantially if we consider a percentage (ex. 50%) of recycled or reused feedstock (Figure 43). Varying the

percentage of reused/recycled feedstock or reused/recycled material at collection allow users to explore different lifecycle scenario and circular options.

Figure 43 Case Study (CAR DASHBOARD) – MCI with recycled feedstock

6.5 Conclusions

An informative lifecycle analysis for an automotive interior product has been performed for energy, carbon footprint, cost, water, manufacturing waste, and a Material Circularity Indicator. An established methodology for material selection during the Concept Design phase has demonstrated the potential for reducing the life cycle environmental impact and improving the economics of the product. The benefits of a circular product over a simple linear or closed loop product cycle were demonstrated by analysis of the flow of materials. Further studies should include cost considerations in the manufacturing, transport and use phases. Improvements to the social and environmental aspects are dealt with in the WP 7 *Life Cycle Thinking*.

For the full case study reports please refer to Appendix.

7 List of EcoBulk partners

Full Name	Short Name	Country
Akzo Nobel Industrial Coatings Ab	AKZO NOBEL	SE
Amiplas	AIMPLAS	ES
Asociacion Espanola De Normalizacion	UNE	ES
Bellver	BELLVER	ES
Centro Ricerche Fiat Scpa	CR FIAT SCPA	IT
Conenor Oy	Conenor	FI
Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche	CNR	IT
Cranfield University	CRANFIELD UNI	UK
Exergy Ltd	EXERGY	UK
Granta Design Ltd	GRANTA DESIGN	UK
Innovacio I Recerca Industrial I Sostenible SI	IRIS	ES
Institut Technologique Fcba (Foretcellulose Boisconstruction Ameublement)	FCBA	FR
Instituto Tecnologico Del Embalaje, Transporte Y Logistica	ITENE	ES
International Solid Waste Association	ISWA	AT
Kastamonu Entegre Agac Sanayi Ve Ticaret Anonim Sirketi	KEAS	TR
Kneia SI	KNEIA	ES
MAIER S Coop	MAIER	ES
Microcab Industries Ltd	MICROCAB	UK
Moretti Compact	MORETTI	IT
Netcomposites Limited Coventive	NETCOMPOSITES Coventive	UK
Next Technology Tecnotessile Società Nazionale Di Ricerca R.L.	NTT	IT
Oakdene Hollins Limited	OAKDENE HOLLINS	UK
Servico Intermunicipalizado De Gestao De Residuos Do Grande Porto	LIPOR	PT
Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	NL
Technoplants Srl	Technoplants	IT
Tecnaro Gesellschaft zur industriellen Anwendung Nachwachsender Rohstoffe mbh	Tecnaro GmbH	DE
Tomra Sorting GmbH	TS	DE
Universitat Politecnica De Catalunya	UPC	ES
Vertech Group	VERTECH	FR

Table 4 List of Partners in EcoBulk Consortium

8 References

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- 9) Granta MaterialUniverse™, Granta Design Limited, Cambridge, UK, 2017 (www.grantadesign.com)